

FAT tumor suppressor homolog 4 (Drosophila) / FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : FAT4, is also known as the cadherin-related family member 11 (CDHR11). FAT family members are targets of systems medicine in the fields of oncology and neurology and FAT4 upstream of Yes1 associated transcriptional regulator (YAP), an effector of the Hippo signaling pathway, acts as a key regulator of mammalian neurogenesis. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of FAT4, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of FAT4 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4)

Calcium-dependent adhesion (Cadherins) are a class of type-1 transmembrane proteins, and depend on calcium (Ca^{2+}) ions to function. In a review, Alimperti and Andreadis [13] focus on the role of Cadherins which are cell adhesion molecules that form adherens junctions that lets cells adhere to each other. Extracellular cadherin domains mediate cell-cell adhesion, while the intracellular cytoplasmic tail associates with multiple adaptors and signaling proteins; These are collectively called cadherin adhesome.

FAT4, is also known as the cadherin-related family member 11 (CDHR11). The

CDHRs do not fit into the major cadherin or protocadherin families as they are phylogenetically separated. The encoded proteins comprise at least two typical, consecutive cadherin motifs and their overall domain organization differs from the members of the both the major cadherin and protocadherin, family.

Arachidonic acid and eicosapentaenoic acid are important forerunners for the production of prostaglandins and other hormone-like eicosanoid molecules as these fatty acids are synthesized by animals via elongation and desaturation of precursor fatty acids such as linoleic acid (18:2 $\Delta^{9,12}$) and alpha-linolenic acid (18:3 $\Delta^{9,12,15}$). citet-Watts:1999isolation identified a Δ^5 fatty acid desaturase gene (FAT-4) from the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* and expressed this gene product in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and demonstrated that it readily converted di-homo-gamma-linolenic acid (20:3 $\Delta^{8,11,14}$) to arachidonic acid (20:4 $\Delta^{5,8,11,14}$). The FAT-4 Δ^5 -desaturase also acts on a number of other substrates, including fatty acids that do not contain a double bond at the Δ^8 position.

Combining protein motif search and gene finding methods, Höng et al. [14] focused on identifying new human genes of the cadherin superfamily proteins, which represent a major group of cell-cell adhesion receptors contributing to embryonic neuronal morphogenesis. They used models for three cadherin protein motifs to identify the exon-intron structure of new genes and found CDH-J, PCDH-J and FAT-J. Further, they classified the predicted proteins PCDH-J and FAT-J into protocadherin and FAT-like subfamilies, respectively.

FAT-1/2/3/4 are Cadherin superfamily members homologous to *Drosophila* FAT, functioning as a positive regulator of PCP in the *Drosophila* wing. Complete coding sequence (CDS) for human FAT1 (NM_005245.3) and FAT2 (NM_001447.1) are available, while artificial CDS for human FAT3 (XM_926199 and XM_936538) and partial CDS for FAT4 (NM_024582.2). Via comparative integromics, Katoh and Katoh [15] determined complete CDS of human FAT-3/4 and FAT4. Specifically, they found that FAT4 gene encoded a 4924-aa protein with extracellular 34 Cadherin repeats, two Laminin G (LamG) domains and three EGF domains. Among FAT-1/2/3 orthologs, they identified conserved cytoplasmic VCSVxPxLP and SDYxS motifs. Further, domain architecture comparison and phylogenetic analysis revealed that FAT-1/2/3 were divergent from FAT4. Particularly, they observed that FAT4 mRNA was expressed in fetal brain, infant brain, brain tumor and colorectal cancer. Thus they revealed FAT family members as targets of systems medicine in the fields of oncology and neurology.

Tissue organization in *Drosophila* is regulated by the core planar cell polarity (PCP) proteins Frizzled, Dishevelled, Prickle, Van Gogh and Flamingo. Studies have also identified another group of *Drosophila* PCP proteins, consisting of the protocadherins FAT and Dachsous (DS) and the transmembrane protein Four-jointed (Fj). In *Drosophila*, FAT represses fj transcription, and DS represses FAT activity in PCP. Saburi et al. [16] showed that FAT4 had a key role in vertebrate PCP. They observed that loss of FAT4 disturbed oriented cell divisions and tubule elongation during kidney development, thus leading to cystic kidney disease. Further, they found that FAT4 genetically interacted with the PCP genes VANGL2 and FJX1 in cyst formation, while repressing the expression of the latter. Their data indicated that FAT4 regulated vertebrate PCP and that loss of PCP signaling might underlie some cystic diseases in humans.

Periventricular neuronal heterotopia (i.e mislocalization of cortical neurons), can arise from neuronal progenitors that fail to negotiate aspects of regulated proliferation and differentiation of neural stem cells before the generation and migration of neurons in the cerebral cortex which are central aspects of mammalian development. Cappello et al. [17] showed that mutations in genes encoding the receptor-ligand cadherin pair DCHS1 and FAT4, led to a recessive syndrome in humans that included periventricular neuronal heterotopia. By reducing the expression of DCHS1 or FAT4 within mouse embryonic neuroepithelium, they observed increased progenitor cell numbers and reduced their differentiation into neurons, thus resulting in the heterotopic accumulation of cells below the neuronal layers in the neocortex. Further, they observed that these effects were countered by concurrent knockdown of Yes1 associated transcriptional regulator (YAP), an effector of the Hippo signaling pathway. Their findings pointed to the fact that DCHS1 and FAT4 upstream of YAP, were key regulators of mammalian neurogenesis.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [18] in <https://www.cs.cornell.edu/>

people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [19] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [19].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [20]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity

analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [21], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [18] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [18]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [22], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. FAT4 related synergies

Note - FAT4 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and FDR ≤ 0.001 , in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of FAT4 were recorded.

3.1.1. FAT4 - Individual genes

The following genes were found to show high rankings along with FAT4 - microsomal glutathione S-transferase 1 (MGST1), G protein-coupled receptor class C group 5 member A (GPCR5A), V-set and immunoglobulin domain containing 2 (VSIG2), toll-like 1 (TLL1), mucolipin TRP cation channel 3 (MCOLN3), erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3), protein kinase C zeta (PRKCZ), ST6 N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 2 (ST6GALNAC2), RAP1 GTPase activating protein (RAP1GAP), calpain 6 (CAPN6), secretagoin, EF-hand calcium binding protein (SCGN), solute carrier family 4 member 4 (SLC4A4), progesterone receptor (PGR), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1LH), PITPNM family member 3 (PITPNM3), ezrin (EZR), BMP and activin membrane bound inhibitor (BAMBI), protein kinase C and casein kinase substrate in neurons 2

(PACSIN2), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 2 (EEF1A2), mesothelin (MSLN), junctophilin 1 (JPH1), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), Rap guanine nucleotide exchange factor like 1 (RAPGEFL1), protein arginine methyltransferase 8 (PRMT8), RNA binding motif protein 24 (RBM24), leucine rich repeat containing 31 (LRRC31), peroxisomal biogenesis factor 5 like (PEX5L), acyl-CoA dehydrogenase long chain (ACADL), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), melanophilin (MLPH), 24-dehydrocholesterol reductase (DHCR24), SSX family member 2 interacting protein (SSX2IP), endothelin converting enzyme 1 (ECE1), tetraspanin 1 (TSPAN1), interferon regulatory factor 6 (IRF6), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), solute carrier family 16 member 7 (SLC16A7), periplakin (PPL), cyclin and CBS domain divalent metal cation transport mediator 1 (CNNM1), citron rho-interacting serine/threonine kinase (CIT), nuclear factor, erythroid 2 (NFE2), myelin regulatory factor (MYRF), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 4 (PEL blood group) (ABCC4), SRY-box transcription factor 9 (SOX9), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 2 (PCSK2), tubulin alpha 4a (TUBA4A), G protein subunit alpha z (GNAZ), filamin C (FLNC), coiled-coil domain containing 136 (CCDC136), kallikrein related peptidase 8 (KLK8), proline rich and Gla domain 3 (PRRG3), microtubule associated scaffold protein 2 (MTUS2), brain expressed X-linked 2 (BEX2), serine/threonine kinase 26 (STK26), BICD family like cargo adaptor 1 (BICDL1), ETS homologous factor (EHF), PILR alpha associated neural protein (PIANP), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), PR/SET domain 16 (PRDM16), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), immunoglobulin like domain containing receptor 2 (ILDR2), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 7B (THSD7B), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), glutamate decarboxylase like 1 (GADL1), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), scavenger receptor cysteine rich family member with 4 domains (SSC4D), solute carrier family 26 member 7 (SLC26A7), lipocalin 2 (LCN2), cadherin 8 (CDH8), family with sequence similarity 124 member A (FAM124A), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), chondrolectin (CHODL), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit gamma1 (GABRG1), carboxypeptidase A3 (CPA3), neuropeptide Y receptor Y1 (NPY1R), hyperpolarization activated cyclic nucleotide gated potassium channel 1 (HCN1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), WNK lysine deficient protein kinase 2 (WNK2), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), solute carrier family 16 member 9 (SLC16A9), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), phospholipase A and acyltransferase 5 (HRASLS5 / PLAAT5), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein (PHYHIP), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), kallikrein related peptidase 7 (KLK7), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9), mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), DLG associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), heparan sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 2 (HS6ST2), potassium two pore domain channel

subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), angiopoietin like 7 (ANGPTL7), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), syntrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), myosin ID (MYO1D), reprimin, TP53 dependent G2 arrest mediator homolog (RPRM), cadherin 4 (CDH4), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member A3 (ALDH1A3), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), limbic system associated membrane protein (LSAMP), potassium voltage-gated channel interacting protein 4 (KCNIP4), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), metallophosphoesterase domain containing 1 (MPPED1), forkhead box I2 (FOXI2), keratin 16 (KRT16), pyroglutamylated RFamide peptide receptor (QRFP), phospholipase A2 group IIA (PLA2G2A), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), ankyrin repeat domain 35 (ANKRD35), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2) and collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to tabulate 2nd order combinations of FAT4 with these genes, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t FAT4 with FAT4 – > MGST1 / GPRC5A / VSIG2 / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ERBB3 / PRKCZ / ST6GALNAC2 / RAP1GAP / CAPN6 / SCGN / SLC4A4 / PGR / ABCB1 / PTHLH / PITPNM3 / EZR / BAMBI / PACSIN2 / NTSR1 / EEF1A2 / MSLN / JPH1 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / COBL / RAPGEFL1 / PRMT8 / RBM24 / LRRC31 / PEX5L / ACADL / IL1RL1 / MLPH / DHCR24 / SSX2IP / ECE1 / TSPAN1 / IRF6 / PLPPR4 / SLC16A7 / PPL / CNNM1 / CIT / NFE2 / MYRF / ABCC4 / SOX9 / PCSK2 / TUBA4A / GNAZ / FLNC / CCDC136 / KLK8 / PRRG3 / MTUS2 / BEX2 / STK26 / BICDL1 / EHF / PIANP / COL2A1 / MDGA2 / PRDM16 / MAEL / ILDR2 / SUSD4 / THSD7B / GALNT13 / GADL1 / GABRB2 / SSC4D / SLC26A7 / LCN2 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / CHODL / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / SH3RF2 / FBXO32 / CLIC6 / COX6B2 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / GABRG1 / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / DEFB1 / WNK2 / PHYHIPL / SLC16A9 / SCN3B / HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / KLK7 / PCSK9 / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / HS6ST2 / KCNK3 / ANO5 / ANGPTL7 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / CSDC2 / SNTG2 / CES4A / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / RPRM / CDH4 / TMEM30B / ALDH1A3 / BEX5 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / LSAMP / KCNIP4 / BCR / MPPED1 / FOXI2 / KRT16 / QRFP / PLA2G2A / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / AFDN-DT / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic FAT4 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS FAT4									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T FAT4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MGST1 - FAT4	17	187	187	201	GPRC5A - FAT4	115	196	238	277
VSIG2 - FAT4	225	191	139	233	TLL1 - FAT4	305	167	204	45
MCOLN3 - FAT4	163	189	297	93	ERBB3 - FAT4	275	294	234	138
PRKCCZ - FAT4	280	109	148	259	ST6GALNAC2 - FAT4	18	280	216	214
RAP1GAP - FAT4	285	290	279	24	CAPN6 - FAT4	151	184	294	219
SCGN - FAT4	205	135	213	263	SLC4A4 - FAT4	179	48	175	169
PGR - FAT4	107	190	135	244	ABCB1 - FAT4	236	138	307	74
PTHLH - FAT4	249	266	217	113	PITPNM3 - FAT4	242	153	218	182
EZR - FAT4	243	143	180	304	BAMBI - FAT4	228	31	179	256
PACSIN2 - FAT4	180	255	122	168	NTSR1 - FAT4	258	289	229	127
EEF1A2 - FAT4	49	231	254	297	MSLN - FAT4	214	281	241	110
JPH1 - FAT4	259	186	265	80	GRIK5 - FAT4	155	158	105	271
RUNDC3B - FAT4	209	257	142	134	COBL - FAT4	270	277	220	50
RAPGEFL1 - FAT4	232	192	34	288	PRMT8 - FAT4	286	265	253	76
RBM24 - FAT4	247	171	41	272	LRRC31 - FAT4	261	263	240	99
PEX5L - FAT4	208	146	276	62	ACADL - FAT4	34	151	163	302
ILIRL1 - FAT4	274	230	243	98	MLPH - FAT4	168	245	191	152
DHCR24 - FAT4	198	213	44	276	SSX2IP - FAT4	74	164	169	188
ECE1 - FAT4	277	199	215	262	TSPAN1 - FAT4	301	224	272	56
IRF6 - FAT4	82	154	197	290	PLPPR4 - FAT4	273	297	268	129
SLC16A7 - FAT4	204	233	201	8	PPL - FAT4	227	198	285	255
CNNM1 - FAT4	246	259	145	282	CIT - FAT4	282	182	178	30
NFE2 - FAT4	44	223	151	305	MYRF - FAT4	304	211	260	105
ABCC4 - FAT4	29	236	203	303	SOX9 - FAT4	129	254	258	220
PCSK2 - FAT4	187	249	284	118	TUBA4A - FAT4	165	237	190	228
GNAZ - FAT4	271	275	245	283	FLNC - FAT4	210	165	66	177
CCDC136 - FAT4	255	14	174	222	KLK8 - FAT4	221	307	269	81
PRRG3 - FAT4	253	183	288	65	MTUS2 - FAT4	278	221	302	208
BEX2 - FAT4	291	142	273	63	STK26 - FAT4	229	214	162	137
BICDL1 - FAT4	237	283	237	172	EHF - FAT4	283	152	293	278
PIANP - FAT4	248	155	185	79	COL2A1 - FAT4	178	88	219	215
MDGA2 - FAT4	169	273	227	159	PRDM16 - FAT4	148	28	182	251
MAEL - FAT4	222	271	291	92	ILDR2 - FAT4	170	301	301	94
SUSD4 - FAT4	146	296	198	75	THSD7B - FAT4	250	162	159	95
GALNT13 - FAT4	181	256	207	135	GADL1 - FAT4	226	250	277	132

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FAT4 VS Individual members.

ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of FAT4-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS FAT4

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T FAT4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
GABRB2 - FAT4	184	299	232	83	SSC4D - FAT4	220	149	168	292
SLC26A7 - FAT4	233	295	283	88	LCN2 - FAT4	244	144	195	39
CDH8 - FAT4	65	242	137	268	FAM124A - FAT4	262	288	257	252
CCDC3 - FAT4	142	101	230	154	CHODL - FAT4	288	195	186	48
NCAM2 - FAT4	147	119	143	232	SLC26A2 - FAT4	267	253	235	299
SH3RF2 - FAT4	192	180	193	211	FBXO32 - FAT4	202	212	304	237
CLIC6 - FAT4	199	70	173	294	COX6B2 - FAT4	287	264	274	106
AKNAD1 - FAT4	290	156	160	14	SGPP2 - FAT4	158	243	286	160
GABRG1 - FAT4	298	258	256	150	CPA3 - FAT4	177	260	212	96
NPY1R - FAT4	223	272	290	70	HCN1 - FAT4	216	244	296	91
DEFB1 - FAT4	296	286	299	111	WNK2 - FAT4	188	282	305	194
PHYHIPL - FAT4	193	87	244	267	SLC16A9 - FAT4	203	129	252	158
SCN3B - FAT4	161	166	189	280	HRASLS5 - FAT4	197	298	266	53
BDKRB2 - FAT4	284	218	263	71	PHYHIP - FAT4	302	293	255	58
NSG1 - FAT4	7	238	172	306	KLK7 - FAT4	213	248	295	84
PCSK9 - FAT4	260	284	300	104	MUC3A - FAT4	217	178	282	155
DLGAP1 - FAT4	125	252	150	203	HS6ST2 - FAT4	123	247	249	239
KCNK3 - FAT4	152	51	248	192	ANO5 - FAT4	263	194	236	298
ANGPTL7 - FAT4	149	232	153	279	MBOAT1 - FAT4	45	228	147	213
TPSAB1 - FAT4	185	150	206	140	CSDC2 - FAT4	127	235	275	179
SNTG2 - FAT4	272	300	262	78	CES4A - FAT4	218	202	165	224
SLCO2A1 - FAT4	138	112	194	287	MYO1D - FAT4	174	168	176	257
RPRM - FAT4	206	251	292	68	CDH4 - FAT4	194	181	287	77
TMEM30B - FAT4	279	95	231	307	ALDH1A3 - FAT4	139	201	264	116
BEX5 - FAT4	99	148	261	149	SDR42E1 - FAT4	196	131	247	163
MAFF - FAT4	143	234	209	295	LSAMP - FAT4	171	279	202	97
KCNIP4 - FAT4	297	305	303	114	BCR - FAT4	66	207	154	253
MPPED1 - FAT4	234	239	270	72	FOXI2 - FAT4	300	276	224	102
KRT16 - FAT4	266	204	251	41	QRFPR - FAT4	303	285	306	85
PLA2G2A - FAT4	299	291	289	174	LAMB3 - FAT4	172	219	9	254
TPSB2 - FAT4	110	306	184	147	AFDN-DT - FAT4	289	268	242	199
ANKRD35 - FAT4	211	262	208	175	SREBF2 - FAT4	201	210	239	176
COL15A1 - FAT4	306	287	298	125					

Table 2: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between FAT4 VS Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t FAT4

MGST1 / GPRC5A / VSIG2 / TLL1 / MCOLN3 ...
 ERBB3 / PRKCZ / ST6GALNAC2 / RAP1GAP ...
 CAPN6 / SCGN / SLC4A4 / PGR / ABCB1 ...
 PTHLH / PITPNM3 / EZR / BAMBI / PACSIN2 ...
 NTSR1 / EEF1A2 / MSLN / JPH1 / GRIK5 ...
 RUNDC3B / COBL / RAPGEFL1 / PRMT8 / RBM24 ...
 LRRC31 / PEX5L / ACADL / IL1RL1 / MLPH ...
 DHCR24 / SSX2IP / ECE1 / TSPAN1 / IRF6 ...
 PLPPR4 / SLC16A7 / PPL / CNNM1 / CIT ...
 NFE2 / MYRF / ABCC4 / SOX9 / PCSK2 ...
 TUBA4A / GNAZ / FLNC / CCDC136 / KLK8 ...
 PRRG3 / MTUS2 / BEX2 / STK26 / BICDL1 ...
 EHF / PIANP / COL2A1 / MDGA2 / PRDM16 ...
 MAEL / ILDR2 / SUS4 / THSD7B / GALNT13 ...
 GADL1 / GABRB2 / SSC4D / SLC26A7 / LCN2 ...
 CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / CHODL / NCAM2 ...
 SLC26A2 / SH3RF2 / FBXO32 / CLIC6 / COX6B2 ...
 AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / GABRG1 / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 ...
 DEFB1 / WNK2 / PHYHIPL / SLC16A9 / SCN3B ...
 HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / KLK7 ...
 PCSK9 / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / HS6ST2 / KCNK3 ...
 ANO5 / ANGPTL7 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / CSDC2 ...
 SNTG2 / CES4A / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / RPRM ...
 CDH4 / TMEM30B / ALDH1A3 / BEX5 / SDR42E1 ...
 MAFF / LSAMP / KCNIP4 / BCR / MPPED1 / FOXI2 ...
 KRT16 / QRFPR / PLA2G2A / LAMB3 / TPSB2 ...
 AFDN-DT / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1 FAT4

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between FAT4 and Individual members.

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